

Policy Brief

Improving the Post-Implementation Experience of Older People Receiving Old-Aged Allowances in Nepal.

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- ✓ *Integrating health insurance scheme with allowance distribution could improve older people's financial obligations.*
- ✓ *Community-based caretakers require institutional recognition and financial support.*

<u>Findings</u>	<u>Recommendations</u>
<i>No access to health insurance scheme</i>	<i>Simplification of administrative procedure</i>
<i>No acknowledgement of caretaker contribution</i>	<i>Integration of health insurance program with allowance distribution</i>
<i>Administrative inefficiency</i>	<i>Supporting caretakers financially</i>

Executive Summary

The evidence shows some major challenges such as administrative hurdles, communication gaps, incorrect information in documents like citizenship, renewal of allowance-related documents, no access to national health insurance schemes, and ignorance of caretaker contribution in well-being of elderly people.

This policy brief recommends in simplifying the administrative procedures, integrating health insurance program with the distribution of allowance through banks, and enabling financial support for caretakers in community-based care homes, in order to increase satisfaction and improve effectiveness of old-age allowance program

Problem Statement

Nepal's Old-Age Allowance Program provides financial support to older persons, particularly those from disadvantaged and socially vulnerable groups. The program performed well in ensuring timely and regular payment however, it declines after challenges like administrative hurdles and ineffective service delivery.

Based on evidence, the overall satisfaction among elderly people is reduced by:

- Complex administrative procedures
- Difficulty in document renewal process
- Correction of Date of Birth (DOB) mistake in the citizenship
- Lack of proper grievances handling
- Limited communication between elderly people and local authorities

- No access to health insurance scheme
- No support for caretakers in any form by external stakeholders

These challenges reduce the satisfaction on allowance program among elderly people.

Findings

The study found that beneficiaries reported high satisfaction with:

- Access to allowance
- Regularity of payments

However, satisfaction was considerably lower regarding:

- Sufficiency of the allowance amount
- Administrative efficiency
- Program management

And, several post-implementation challenges emerged. They are:

1. Administrative Challenge

Elderly people are required to travel to their permanent place of residence to renew documents, even when living somewhere else, temporarily.

For many older persons like someone aged 70 years and above, issues like

- Physical stress
- Travel expenses
- Administrative delays

Communication gaps between elderly people and government agencies, further complicate access to services and grievance resolution.

2. No Access to Health Insurance

Many elderly people, particularly those living in care homes, remain outside Nepal's national health insurance system. Without insurance coverage, elderly people struggle to meet healthcare expenses associated with chronic illnesses such as hypertension, diabetes, asthma, heart issues, and other age-related conditions.

As a result, with a source of allowance payments are quite insufficient to maintain their overall health and cover medical expenses.

3. No Support for Caretakers

Community-based care homes depend heavily on caretakers who provide essential services to older persons on a daily basis.

Despite their contribution, caretakers receive:

- No regular salary
- Limited social recognition
- No support from local governments

This affects significantly on staff motivation and challenges the sustainability of community-based care homes.

Recommendations

1. Simplification of administrative procedures

Alternatives like Allowing beneficiaries to renew allowance-related documents from their temporary residence facilitated by the local ward office, by digital integration of service among government offices.

This would then reduce travel costs, administrative burdens, and reduce physical stress for elderly people.

2. Integration of health insurance program with allowance distribution

The insurance board of Nepal, in collaboration with government and banks could initiate a campaign of providing health insurance schemes by deducting insurance premium from the beneficiary's bank account under their consent, and issuing them an insurance policy.

As a result, elderly people would be easily enrolled in the national health insurance scheme.

3. Support for caretakers

Local government should conduct a survey, identify the care homes, and workers associated with them, and then prepare a legal framework that can facilitate in supporting them financially by ensuring at least minimum salary is provided.

Role of Agencies

Recommendations	Agency	Impact
Simplification of administrative procedures	Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration and Local Government	Medium
Enrolment in Health Insurance Scheme	Health Insurance Board and Commercial Banks, Local Government	High
Supporting caretakers	Local Government and Ministry of Women, Children and Senior Citizens	Medium

Possible Outcomes

- Reduction in administrative burdens for elderly people.
- Increased enrolment in the national health insurance scheme.
- Improved access to healthcare for older persons.
- Morally strong community-based caretakers.
- Increased overall satisfaction with the Old-Age Allowance program.

Conclusion

The old-age allowance (OAA) program in Nepal has provided financial support for elderly people in giving them dignified life, especially in time of ageing. Nevertheless, improving administrative inefficiency, initiating access to healthcare schemes, and acknowledging contributions of caretakers by supporting them financially, it would significantly increase satisfaction to even higher level.

The Evidence in this Policy Brief is based on,

Ghimire, B. (2026). Determinants of Satisfaction: A Survey-Based Study of Social Security Allowance among the Elderly People from Banepa and Kathmandu Valley Using Regression Analysis. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*.

<https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2026.100600098>.

Government of Nepal, Ministry of Women, Children and Senior Citizens.

Health Insurance Board, Nepal.

Informal conversation with Stakeholders including Government Officers, Caretakers, Activists, during the survey.